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Nextfood - Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system

Practice Abstract #4: Master manual for case development, first draft

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A central part of the Nextfood project is the 12 case studies conducted in 10 countries on 3 continents. All these cases are attempting to transform their education models to align with the Nextfood approach. Not only are we trying to make the change, but we are also researching the process and the outcomes. In this document, the case leaders will find specific instructions on how to develop their case towards the transformational goals of the project. Primarily, this document describes the iterative process of planning, implementing and reflecting, which is to be followed by each case. Specific instructions are given to each of the three phases and appendices contain templates in relation to those specific instructions as well as examples from the past cycle of project activities. We recommend anyone interested in trying out these action learning elements to have a look at these instructions and appendices.

We believe that a successful transition to a situation where action learning is the norm for educating the future generation of professionals, we need to concretise and make guidelines as to how such an approach is done. This document constitutes one of the pillars of the foundation upon which the next generation of education system is built. This manual is written in such a way that it should be easily accessible for practitioners who would like to adapt to the Nextfood approach.